

INNOVATION HUB

FLEXIBILITY

NEFI Innovation Hubs are specialised networks led by renowned research institutions. They initiate highly relevant research and innovation projects.

Flexibility

Target groups: all sectors

Services offered by the NEFI Innovation Hubs

- NEFI Technology Talks:
A range of networking and information events
- Support throughout the entire innovation process: From project idea, application submission, to impact assessment
- Access to state-of-the-art laboratory infrastructure
- Effective dissemination and exploitation of solutions and results

Flexible technologies are crucial for industrial transformation. They promote renewable energy, store surplus energy, and release it when needed, making the energy supply more stable. Additionally, energy-intensive processes can be scheduled during times of high renewable generation, reducing fossil fuel use and smoothing peak loads, which lowers costs and makes systems more resilient.

KEY FOCUS AREAS

Simulation and optimisation methods to identify and quantify flexibilisation potentials

Prediction of market prices

Unlocking flexibilisation potentials in ongoing processes (operational optimisation)

Development of technologies for data collection, processing, and analysis

CONTACT DETAILS

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HUB CO-LEADS

